

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

EFFECTS OF ASPIRIN ON CARDIOVASCULAR EVENTS AND BLEEDING IN THE HEALTHY ELDERLY

¹Dr. Muhammad Umar Farooq,²Dr. Khawaja Mashood Arif,³Dr. Laraib Khurshid¹MO, BHU 20/14L, Sahiwal.²Demonstrator AJK Medical College, Muzaffarabad AJK.³WMO, CMH Muzaffarabad AJK.**Abstract**

Aspirin is a deep-rooted therapy considered cardiovascular events' secondary prevention. Therefore, Aspirin role in cardiovascular disease' primary preclusion is blurred, specifically in older persons, as they have amplified risk.

This research is based on the enrolled community-dwelling women and men, from 2010 to 2014 in the United States of America and Australia who were seventy years old (or ≥ 65 years of age) with no cardiovascular dementia, disability or disease. We assure that participants were randomly dispensed to take 100 mg of aspirin (enteric-coated) or placebo. The main endpoint was a compound of dementia, persistent disability or death; these endpoint results are documented accordingly. A secondary endpoint consists of core hemorrhage and fatal coronary heart disease (commonly known as cardiovascular disease, nonfatal or fatal stroke, nonfatal myocardial infarction, stroke or heart failure hospitalization).

The trial was enrolled with 19114 patients of whom 9525 were allocated to obtain aspirin and 9589 to obtain placebo. After a follow up of 4.7 years' median, the cardiovascular disease rate was 10.7 events per one thousand people per year in the group of aspirin and 11.3 events per one thousand persons per year in the group of placebo (with hazard ratio, 0.95; CI confidence interval 95%, 0.83 to 1.08). Major hemorrhage rate was 8.6 events per one thousand persons and 6.2 events per one thousand persons per year (with the hazard ratio, 1.38; 95% confidence interval, 1.18 to 1.62; $P = 0.001$). Low-dose aspirin use as a major strategy of prevention in older adults may result in an important high risk of major hemorrhage than placebo.

Keywords: *Cardiovascular events; Aspirin Effects; Elderly adults*

Corresponding author:

Dr. Muhammad Umar Farooq,
MO, BHU 20/14L,
Sahiwal.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Umar Farooq et al., *Effects Of Aspirin On Cardiovascular Events And Bleeding In The Healthy Elderly.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(10).

1.0 INTRODUCTION:

The diseases of cardiovascular among the major reasons for death and disability in elder adults and defensive interventions for these diseases are considered high priority. The most widely used agent is low-dose aspirin for the cardiovascular disease prevention. Basically, its efficiency has been recognized as the trials of secondary prevention through which the advantages linked with declining the rates of both ischemic stroke and myocardial infarction have represented to overshadow the hemorrhage risk (Armstrong, 2014).

In the trials of primary prevention, linking participants which considered the cardiovascular disease risk was generally lower than the seen risk in trials of secondary prevention, the risks, and advantages of low-dose aspirin seems finely balanced. Low-dose aspirin's role as a strategy of primary prevention is discussed. In elderly persons, the cardiovascular disease risk is much higher and the probable advantages of aspirin may appropriately be higher than in younger persons. Therefore, bleeding increase risk has also been experiential in elderly people (Donadini, Bellesini and Squizzato, 2018).

2.0 METHODS:

2.1 Trial Design

We managed this double-blind, placebo-controlled trial clinically to describe the effects of 100 mg daily dosage use of enteric-coated aspirin, specifically in older adults. We used Bayer Pharma (Germany) offered aspirin and placebo but it had no other participants in the trial. Data was gathered through the website of the "Department of Epidemiology and Preventive Medicine" Australia at Monash University, this trial also approved by the committee of ethics.

2.2 Trial Participants

Adults of the United States of America and Australia were the basic participants of this trial, who were either seventy years or older. It was required for participants to be free from overt cerebrovascular disease, a disease of the overt coronary heart, dementia diagnosis, atrial fibrillation, clinically important physical disability, anemia, bleeding risk and any inability to take the main medicine of trial "aspirin".

2.3 Trial Procedure

All those respondents who had adherence to pill absorption rate, as analyzed by the count of the pill, of 80% during one month placebo period according to 1:1 ratio, to take aspirin or placebo. According to

trial age and center, randomization was stratified (from 65 to ≥ 80 years). In-person visits annually have been monitored; through the history of the medical record which maintained by regular telephone calls to inspire trial retention and clinical data collection facilitation. Investigators, general practitioners, trial participants were uninformed of the assignments of trial group (Donadini, Bellesini and Squizzato, 2018).

2.3.1 Cardiovascular Events

As per the explanation cardiovascular disease was secondary end level of this trial which is fundamentally a complex of heart's fatal coronary disease, fatal and nonfatal stroke, heart failure hospitalization and nonfatal myocardial infarction. Initial individual factors about endpoint but analyzed in the post hoc assessment to help in the endpoint interpretation composition (Gryglewski, 2016).

It is defined that fatal coronary disease as death through myocardial infarction, immediate death by cardiac reason and any other reason for death which is associated with coronary heart disease. Fatal stroke distinct as any death by the reason rupture in the extra or intra-cranial arterial of cerebral system (Jain, 2015).

2.3.2 Major Haemorrhagic Events

Another pre-defined secondary level endpoint was core hemorrhage; it was a hemorrhagic stroke composition, intracranial bleeding or significant clinically extracranial bleeding. This bleeding was described that managed to hospitalization, transfusion, surgery, prolongation of hospitalization or finally death (Lisa, 2016).

2.3.3 Statistical Analysis

We used Cox proportional models for hazards, in the assessment of intention to treat and for the comparison of aspirin group with another placebo group regarding endpoints of time to events. Reason specific hazards were associated between both groups, other than specific deaths which included in interest endpoints preserved as censoring events.

In multiple comparisons CI (confidence intervals) were not adjusted, accordingly, P values do not exist for non-pre-specified and secondary endpoints, only P values present for important hemorrhage due to safety endpoint. Accordingly, assumptions of proportional hazards were verified as a null hypothesis in the regression model to zero slopes; P

values were originated to be higher than 0.1 which further indicate all endpoint assumption's satisfaction. We use cumulative incidences to represent event risk and these cumulative incidences were further based on regression models competing for risks (Nelson *et al.*, 2015).

3.0 RESULTS:

In the period of four years (from March 2010 to December 2014) 19114 patients were registered in this trial and experienced 9525 aspirin group

participants through randomization and 9589 to the placebo group. The participants of the trial had 74 years median age at randomization, and according to Table 1, 56% were women. Residents (as database showed) of the United States were 13% and Australian were 57%. There is an identical cardiovascular risk profile in the two trial groups. At trial access, 1/3 of the respondents stated usage of statins and 14% described NSAIDs regular use (William, 2016).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics, Cardiovascular Risk Factors, and Treatment of the Participants at Randomization.*

Variable	Aspirin (N = 9525)	Placebo (N = 9589)
	no. (%)	
Male sex	4152 (44)	4179 (44)
Age $\geq$ 74 yr	4806 (50)	4766 (50)
Black race†	451 (5)	450 (5)
Obese‡	2820 (30)	2857 (30)
Smoking		
Current	352 (4)	383 (4)
Former	3909 (41)	3890 (41)
Never	5264 (55)	5316 (55)
Diabetes§	1027 (11)	1030 (11)
Hypertension¶	7065 (74)	7148 (75)
Dyslipidemia	6159 (65)	6308 (66)
Chronic kidney disease**	2456 (26)	2464 (26)
Number of cardiovascular risk factors††		
0 or 1	2935 (31)	2885 (30)
2	3968 (42)	4049 (42)
3 or 4	2622 (28)	2655 (28)
Previous regular aspirin use‡‡	1053 (11)	1041 (11)
Statin use at trial entry§§	3244 (34)	3226 (34)
Use of nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drug at trial entry	1371 (14)	1342 (14)
Use of H ₂ -receptor blocker at trial entry	189 (2)	183 (2)
Use of proton-pump inhibitor at trial entry	2340 (25)	2374 (25)

According cardiovascular event's rate properly show in Table 2 below as the pre-specified rates of cardiovascular disease secondary endpoint did not dissimilar importantly between the placebo and aspirin group 11.3 events per 1000 respondents yearly and 10.7 events per 1000 respondents per year respectively (with the hazard ratio, 0.95;95% and CI, confidence interval, 0.83 to 1.08).

End Point	Overall (N = 19,114)		Aspirin (N = 9525)		Placebo (N = 9589)		Hazard Ratio (95% CI)
	no. of participants with event	rate per 1000 person-yr	no. of participants with event	rate per 1000 person-yr	no. of participants with event	rate per 1000 person-yr	
Cardiovascular disease†	922	10.7	448	10.7	474	11.3	0.95 (0.83–1.08)
Major adverse cardiovascular event‡	701	7.8	329	7.8	372	8.8	0.89 (0.77–1.03)
Fatal cardiovascular disease§	159	1.8	78	1.8	81	1.9	0.97 (0.71–1.33)
Hospitalization for heart failure	171	2.1	88	2.1	83	1.9	1.07 (0.79–1.44)
Fatal or nonfatal myocardial infarction	355	4.0	171	4.0	184	4.3	0.93 (0.76–1.15)
Fatal or nonfatal ischemic stroke¶	315	3.5	148	3.5	167	3.9	0.89 (0.71–1.11)

On June 2017 the intervention phase has been ceased. All assessments were based on those events which happened throughout that final date. 4.7 years was the median follow up; 1.6% of the placebo group and 1.5% in the group of aspirin had been failed to follow-up at the trial ending, 1.2% respondents in every group had decided to withdraw consent. In the last one year of the trial, 62% of respondents based on aspirin group and 64% of that placebo group was yet taking trial intervention which has been assigned (William, 2016).

Major severe cardiovascular events rate was 7.8 in 1000 persons per year as shown in the aspirin group and 8.8 events 1000 persons in one year in the second group of placebo (with the hazard ratio of 0.89:95%

CI, 0.77 to 1.03). Myocardial infarction individual rates, a disease of fatal cardiovascular, ischemic stroke and hospitalization due to heart failure were identical in both groups of aspirin and placebo. There was basically no proof of a discrepancy impact of aspirin on cardiovascular disease risk in any assessment of any sub-group of pre-specified or in the analysis of post hoc of any subgroup regarding probable significance to the cardiovascular disease risk (Wehbeh, Rockey and Barada, 2017).

3.1 Major Haemorrhagic Events

Major hemorrhagic event's rates are specified in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Major Hemorrhagic Events.*

End Point	Overall (N=19,114)	Aspirin (N=9525)	Placebo (N=9589)		Hazard Ratio (95% CI)	P Value	
	no. of participants with event	no. of participants with event	rate per 1000 person-yr	no. of participants with event			rate per 1000 person-yr
Major hemorrhage†	626	361	8.6	265	6.2	1.38 (1.18–1.62)	<0.001
Intracranial bleeding							
Any	179	107	2.5	72	1.7	1.50 (1.11–2.02)	—
Hemorrhagic stroke	77	43	1.0	34	0.8	1.27 (0.81–2.00)	—
Subdural or extradural hemorrhage	61	39	0.9	22	0.5	1.79 (1.06–3.02)	—
Subarachnoid hemorrhage‡	32	18	0.4	14	0.3	1.30 (0.64–2.60)	—
Extracranial bleeding							
Upper gastrointestinal bleeding	137	89	2.1	48	1.1	1.87 (1.32–2.66)	—
Lower gastrointestinal bleeding	127	73	1.7	54	1.3	1.36 (0.96–1.94)	—
Bleeding at another site§	189	101	2.4	88	2.1	1.16 (0.87–1.54)	—
Fatal bleeding							
Fatal major hemorrhage¶	52	28	0.7	24	0.6	1.18 (0.68–2.03)	—
Fatal hemorrhagic stroke	26	13	0.3	13	0.3	1.01 (0.47–2.17)	—

Major hemorrhage rate was 8.6 events per 1000 respondents per year in the group of aspirin as compared with event 6.2 per 1000 respondents per year in the placebo group (with the hazard ration of 1.38; 95% Confidence Interval to 1.62; $P < 0.00$ (Wehbeh, Rockey and Barada, 2017).

4.0 DISCUSSION:

The trial of ASPREE represented that in the old age participants the low-dose usage of aspirin may not provide results in an important lower rate regarding disability-free survival endpoint (with the composition that incorporated the advantages and risks of aspirin) as compared with placebo according to 4.7 years follow up. According to previous trials results, it was expected that advantages of the treatment of aspirin might ascend from the rate of reduction in the events of cardiovascular (Werns, 2015).

Thus, according to this trial, pre-specified secondary endpoint rate about the disease of cardiovascular (with the composition that accounted for the events of cardiovascular comprising intracranial hemorrhage stroke and admission in the hospital due to cardiac failure) was not importantly lesser with aspirin's low dose with placebo. This endpoint hazard ratio was 0.95 (95% Confidence Interval 0.83 to 1.08), which rubric out the major protective effectual possibility of aspirin but is companionable with a highly unexceptional lowering risk up to 17%. Furthermore, the fatal cardiovascular disease rates and heart failure

hospitalization were identical in both aspirin and placebo groups (Ward et al., 2014).

These results' interpretation should take that rate of lower than expected regarding the cardiovascular disease of the trial respondents. The expected rate in the trial protocol was 22.4 events per 1000 respondents per year. The experiential rate was almost half this provided estimate, more likely there is a reflection of the relatively better health of respondents at enrolment and also the decreasing cardiovascular disease rate in two different countries. Due to these stipulations, the accurate advantage that results from lower rate proportionally regarding cardiovascular disease may be lower than the advantage analyzed in studies from preceding years (Nelson et al., 2015).

This trial also represented major hemorrhage risk which was significantly greater with the group of aspirin rather than with the group of placebo. Events of major hemorrhagic primarily involved intracranial bleeding. It is comparative aspirin use effect as compared with another placebo group; on the major hemorrhage risk was consistent over time, advising the respondents who are already receiving aspirin

with low dose have a strong risk of bleeding which may not decrease with constant use (Mah et al., 2014).

These outputs, the large advantage absence on cardiovascular disease joined with bleeding risk with the loss aspirin use, are matching with the meta-analysis results of eight primary trials of prevention, which represented a 17% nonfatal myocardial infarction lower risk and 14% stroke risk, joined with serious bleeding higher risk among respondents who established aspirin than among the placebo groups. It was already expected that bleeding incidence in this trial seemed considerable greater than that incidence in younger participants trials. Due to the reason this trial is registered for older persons and from the general population. The output is likely to be applied broadly to other healthy adults who accordingly recognized for cardiovascular disease prevention. On the contrary, with most preceding basic prevention trials, the present trial did not register respondents on the roots of higher cardiovascular risk (Lisa, 2016).

5.0 CONCLUSION:

Concluding the research paper, it is obviously clear that present randomized trial relating elderly respondents who have no idea about cardiovascular disease and they also do not know about the low dose aspirin usage which resulted in a primary higher risk of core hemorrhage and did not affect in a knowingly cardiovascular disease risk than another placebo group.

REFERENCES:

1. Armstrong, P. (2014). Clopidogrel was more efficacious than aspirin in preventing major cardiovascular events. *Evidence-based Cardiovascular Medicine*, 1(1), p.20.
2. Donadini, M., Bellesini, M. and Squizzato, A. (2018). Aspirin Plus Clopidogrel vs Aspirin Alone for Preventing Cardiovascular Events Among Patients at High Risk for Cardiovascular Events. *JAMA*, 320(6), p.593.
3. Gryglewski, R. (2016). Unusual effects of aspirin on ticlopidine induced thrombolysis. *Thorax*, 55(90002), pp.17S-19.
4. Jain, M. (2015). Review: aspirin reduces CAD events in people with no history of cardiovascular disease, but it increases gastrointestinal bleeding. *Evidence-Based Medicine*, 7(4), pp.111-111.
5. Lisa, F. (2016). Weigh risks and benefits of aspirin in the secondary or primary prevention of cardiovascular events in elderly individuals. *Drugs & Therapy Perspectives*, 20(8), pp.8-11.
6. Mah, I., Leizorovicz, A., Caulin, C. and Bergmann, J. (2014). Aspirin for the Prevention of Cardiovascular Events in the Elderly. *Drugs & Aging*, 20(13), pp.999-1010.
7. Nelson, M., Reid, C., Beilin, L., Donnan, G., Johnston, C., Krum, H., Storey, E., Tonkin, A. and McNeil, J. (2015). Rationale for a Trial of Low-Dose Aspirin for the Primary Prevention of Major Adverse Cardiovascular Events and Vascular Dementia in the Elderly. *Drugs & Aging*, 20(12), pp.897-903.
8. Olga, W. (2015). Enoxaparin sodium and aspirin: bleeding events after renal transplant. *Reactions Weekly*, &NA;(893), p.4.
9. Ward, S., Demos, L., Workman, B. and McNeil, J. (2014). Aspirin for Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Events in the Elderly. *Drugs & Aging*, 29(4), pp.251-258.
10. Wehbeh, A., Rockey, D. and Barada, K. (2017). RE: Risks of Bleeding Recurrence and Cardiovascular Events With Continued Aspirin Use After Lower Gastrointestinal Hemorrhage. *Gastroenterology*, 152(3), pp.669-670.
11. Werns, S. (2010). Effects of aspirin dose on ischaemic events and bleeding after percutaneous coronary intervention: insights from the PCI-CURE study. *Yearbook of Critical Care Medicine*, 2010, pp.75-77.
12. William, N. (2016). Incidence and predictors of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in patients receiving low-dose aspirin for secondary prevention of cardiovascular events in patients with coronary artery disease. *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, 12(18), p.2923.